

Southern Baptists

also known as “Southern Baptist Convention”, “Great Commission Baptists”

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Entry tags: Baptists, Evangelical religion, Protestantism, Evangelicalism, Christian Traditions, Religious Group, North American Religions, American Christianity

The Southern Baptist Convention is an American Protestant Evangelical Christian Tradition formed in 1845. It is currently the largest Protestant denomination in the United States with a membership of 14 million adherents. It has historically emphasized evangelism, personal salvation, the authority of the Bible as the Word of God, and the autonomy of local churches. The Southern Baptist Convention was originally formed in Augusta, GA in an effort to defend slavery (a view which has since been vehemently and retroactively condemned by the Southern Baptist Convention). In the 1980s, conservative Southern Baptists implement the “conservative resurgence” (alternatively called the conservative takeover by its detractors) in which they sought to return to a more traditional understanding of Christian beliefs and practices in response to a perceived drift towards mainline/liberal thinking. This resulted in liberal and moderate Baptists disassociating themselves and forming their own associations. Throughout their history, the Southern Baptist Convention have sought converts to Christianity domestically and abroad through missionary endeavors. In 2010, Southern Baptists voted to be alternatively referred to as “Great Commission Baptists” due to their evangelistic emphasis and international presence. The most well-known Southern Baptist was Billy Graham (1918-2018) who was known for leading mass evangelism events around the world. The Southern Baptist Convention describes itself as “a body of like-minded local churches cooperating together to reach the world with the Good News of Jesus Christ” (sbc.net). A central component of the Southern Baptist Convention’s mission is to “proclaim and minister the Gospel because the love of Christ compels us to do so. God’s call to us is to present the Gospel of Jesus to every person and to make disciples in every town, every city, every state, and every nation. The SBC is committed to sharing the Good News of Jesus Christ with the whole world” (sbc.net). The foundation for contemporary Southern Baptists beliefs is the depiction of the Bible as the Word of God, which is also seen as the authoritative source for Christian beliefs and practices. Southern Baptists have also constructed a summary of their beliefs in a document called “The Baptist Faith and Message”, which represents a broad perspective on 18 topics dealing with theological, ethical, and cultural issues. Southern Baptist churches are not required to affirm or adopt this document, but it does represent a perspective that is widely held among Southern Baptists. Southern Baptist entities include: SBC Executive Committee, International Mission Board, North American Mission Board, Lifeway Christian Resources, GuideStone Financial Resources, Ethics & Religious Liberty Commission, six Seminaries, and the Woman’s Missionary Union.

Date Range: 1845 CE - 2022 CE

Region: Southern Region of United States

Region tags: North America, United States

The origin and main region of Southern Baptists. Often referred to as the "Bible Belt".

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: "The Baptist Story: From English Sect to Global Movement" by Anthony L. Chute, Nathan A. Finn, and Michael A.G. Haykin

– Source 2: "Baptists in America: A History" by Thomas Kidd

– Source 3: "The Baptist Faith and Message" by Charles Kelly Jr., Richard Land, R. Albert Mohler Jr.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

– Source 1: "History of Southern Baptists" by Roger C. Richards

– Source 2: "Southern Baptist Identity: An Evangelical Denomination Faces the Future" ed. by David S. Dockery

– Source 3: "Baptists and the Bible" by Thomas J. Nettles and L. Russ Bush

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

– Source 1: "The Baptist Heritage: Four Centuries of Baptist Witness" by Leon McBeth

– Source 2: "One Sacred Effort: The Cooperative Program of Southern Baptists" by Chad Brand and David Hankins

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.sbc.net/>

– Source 1 Description: Official Website of the Southern Baptist Convention

– Source 2 URL: <https://bfm.sbc.net/bfm2000/>

– Source 2 Description: The Baptist Faith and Message (2000) is the main summary of SBC beliefs.

– Source 3 URL: <https://www.sbc.net/about/what-we-do/mission-vision/>

– Source 3 Description: Mission and Values of the Southern Baptist Convention

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <https://bfm.sbc.net/>

– Source 1 Description: Baptist Faith and Message (2000) is the main document containing a summary of Southern Baptist beliefs.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: Southern Baptists are one among many other Protestant Christian traditions within the United States. In addition to other alternative Christian traditions, various other religious traditions are found within the United States given the diverse freedom of religion that exists.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– No

Notes: Southern Baptists are "exclusivists". This means that they believe that salvation is found in Jesus alone. In other words, Christianity is considered the only true religion. This does not, however, imply that Southern Baptists think they are the only true branch of Christianity. Southern Baptists believe adherents of other Christian denominations/traditions/branches can be authentic Christians outside of the SBC. The Baptist Faith and Message states, "the church [i]s the Body of Christ which includes all of the redeemed of all the ages, believers from every tribe, and tongue, and people, and nation" (BFM Article VI). Alternatively, Southern Baptists could be described as accommodating as they promote the principle of "religious liberty". The Baptist Faith and Message states, "God alone is Lord of the conscience, and He has left it free from the doctrines and commandments of men which are contrary to His Word or not contained in it. Church and state should be separate. The state owes to every church protection and full freedom in the pursuit of its spiritual ends. In providing for such freedom no ecclesiastical group or denomination should be favored by the state more than others. Civil government being ordained of God, it is the duty of Christians to render loyal obedience thereto in all things not contrary to the revealed will of God. The church should not resort to the civil power to carry on its work. The gospel of Christ contemplates spiritual means alone for the pursuit of its ends. The state has no right to impose penalties for religious opinions of any kind. The state has no right to impose taxes for the support of any form of religion. A free church in a free state is the Christian ideal, and this implies the right of free and unhindered access to God on the part of all men, and the right to form and propagate opinions in the sphere of religion without interference by the civil power" (BFM Article XVII).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Notes: While not openly hostile to other religious traditions, Southern Baptist believe themselves to be part of the one true religion implying that other religions are false or demonic.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: Southern Baptists do not advocate the use of violence in response to opposing religions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: To become part of the Southern Baptist Convention, one must become a member of a Southern Baptist Church. Southern Baptist church membership will vary depending on the specific local church requirements. Requirements generally include a confession of faith (i.e. being a Christian), credo baptism (baptism occurring after a profession of faith), and a church membership class. In other words, a person has to choose to join a Southern Baptist church to become a "Southern Baptist". On the requirement of Baptism to become a member see the Baptist Faith and Message Article VII.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: It is typical that baptism is required to become a member within a Southern Baptist church (Baptist Faith and Message Article VII). Baptism is expected to be done after a personal confession of faith (i.e. conversion to Christianity). In some cases this will require a person to be "baptized" a second time. For example, if someone was baptized as an infant (i.e. prior to their ability to have conscious faith in Christ), it is generally not seen to be a valid baptism and thus a hopeful member would be required to undergo baptism by immersion (Adherent placed under the water).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Yes [specify]: Confession of faith in Jesus

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: Christians call proselytization "evangelism" (evangel=good news). Domestic and foreign evangelism is one of the major emphasis of the Southern Baptist Convention. It is expected that all Christians share the Gospel (Good News) of Jesus' life, death and resurrection in the effort that more people become Christians. The expectation for this comes from Jesus' "Great Commission" in which he commands his disciples to "Go therefore and make disciples of all nations, baptizing them in the name of the Father and of the Son and of the Holy Spirit, teaching them to observe all that I have commanded you. And behold, I am with you always, to the end of the age." (Matthew 28:19-20). In other words, since Jesus commands this, all Christians are expected to obey this as a matter of fidelity to God. The motivation comes from the fact that "there is salvation in no one else, for there is no other name under heaven given among me by which we must be saved" (Acts 4:12). The Baptist Faith and Message states, "It is the duty and privilege of every follower of Christ and of every church of the Lord Jesus Christ to endeavor to make disciples of all nations. The new birth of man's spirit by God's Holy Spirit means the birth of love for others. Missionary effort on the part of all rests thus upon a spiritual necessity of the regenerate life, and is expressly and repeatedly commanded in the teachings of Christ. The Lord Jesus Christ has commanded the preaching of the gospel to all nations. It is the duty of every child of God to seek constantly to win the lost to Christ by verbal witness undergirded by a Christian lifestyle, and by other methods in harmony with the gospel of Christ" (BFM Article XI).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– Yes

Notes: Christians call proselytization "evangelism" (evangel=good news). Domestic and foreign evangelism is one of the major emphasis of the Southern Baptist Convention. It is expected that all Christians share the Gospel (Good News) of Jesus' life, death and resurrection in the effort that more people become Christians. The expectation for this comes from Jesus' "Great Commission" in which he commands his disciples to "Go therefore and make disciples of all nations, baptizing them in the name of the Father and of the Son and of the Holy Spirit, teaching them to observe all that I have commanded you. And behold, I am with you always, to the end of the age." (Matthew 28:19-20). In other words, since Jesus commands this, all Christians are expected to obey this as a matter of fidelity to God. The motivation comes from the fact that "there is salvation in no one else, for there is no other name under heaven given among me by which we must be saved" (Acts 4:12). The Baptist Faith and Message states, "It is the duty and privilege of every follower of Christ and of every church of the Lord Jesus Christ to endeavor to make disciples of all nations. The new birth of man's spirit by God's Holy Spirit means the birth of love for others. Missionary effort on the part of all rests thus upon a spiritual necessity of the regenerate life, and is expressly and repeatedly commanded in the teachings of Christ. The Lord Jesus Christ has commanded the preaching of the gospel to all nations. It is the duty of every child of God to seek constantly to win the lost to Christ by verbal witness undergirded by a Christian lifestyle, and by other methods in harmony with the gospel of Christ" (BFM Article XI).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

Notes: In the informal sense, all Christians are expected to be missionaries in that all Christians are expected to share the gospel. In the formal sense, Christians leaders are not required to serve as formal missionaries, but would be expected to regularly share about Christianity through Church service, public, and private interactions). Leaders may be expected to seek out formal missionary opportunities for their church and/or to lead their church's missionary endeavors in other countries. The Baptist Faith and Message states, "It is the duty and privilege of every follower of Christ and of every church of the Lord Jesus Christ to endeavor to make disciples of all nations. The new birth of man's spirit by God's Holy Spirit means the birth of love for others. Missionary effort on the part of all rests thus upon a spiritual necessity of the regenerate life, and is expressly and repeatedly commanded in the teachings of Christ. The Lord Jesus Christ has commanded the preaching of the gospel to all nations. It is the duty of every child of God to seek constantly to win the lost to Christ by verbal witness undergirded by a Christian lifestyle, and by other methods in harmony with the gospel of Christ" (BFM Article XI).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

Notes: In the informal sense, all Christians are expected to be missionaries in that all Christians are expected to share the gospel. In the formal sense, Christians are not required to serve as formal missionaries, but should seek to regularly share about Christianity through Church service, public, and private interactions. Christians may also be expected to seek out formal missionary opportunities within their church (i.e. short term mission trips). The Baptist Faith and Message states, "It is the duty and privilege of every follower of Christ and of every church of the Lord Jesus Christ to endeavor to make disciples of all nations. The new birth of man's spirit by God's Holy Spirit means the birth of love for others. Missionary effort on the part of all rests thus upon a spiritual necessity of the regenerate life, and is expressly and repeatedly commanded in the teachings of Christ. The Lord Jesus Christ has commanded the preaching of the gospel to all nations. It is the duty of every child of God to seek constantly to win the lost to Christ by verbal witness undergirded by a Christian lifestyle, and by other methods in harmony with the gospel of Christ" (BFM Article XI).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Notes: The specific response to this question may come down to what one considers "coercive", but in general Southern Baptists employ a variety of methods to share Christianity openly. Some methods include specific church services, mass evangelistic meetings (i.e. Billy Graham Crusades, revivals, etc.), door-to-door invitations, tracts, and cold encounters (i.e. sharing with strangers). In any of these methods, the goal is to share the message of Jesus' life, death, and resurrection as the solution to humanity's problem of sin, which has estranged humanity from a relationship with God. In other words, by putting faith in Jesus' life, death, and resurrection, a

person is able to be relationally (re)united with God, which is depicted as the fundamental purpose and grounding for human life and activity.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: Southern Baptists do not have official political support, but since the Regan era of the 1980s, they have been closely aligned with the Republican Party. It is not required, however, to vote Republican. In many cases, Southern Baptists focus on political/ethical issues that are at odds with their understanding of Christianity implying that one should vote for the candidate that supports the "biblical view". For example, one should vote for the pro-life candidate (generally implying a republican candidate). Republican candidates will often seek the support of SBC members since the SBC is the largest protestant denomination in America.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Yes

Notes: Southern Baptists generally have a policy of "excommunication" for members who abandon Christianity. The goal of excommunication is restorative rather than punitive. In other words, the rationale behind excommunication is to communicate that the apostate is no longer in good standing within the Christian community and stands in judgement before God. The hope is that an apostate would feel the weight of the loss of fellowship with God and the church and repent of the apostasy. Those who genuinely repent of apostasy/sins are welcomed back within the community. There is some debate among Southern Baptists on whether apostates were genuinely Christians in the first place. Many hold that true Christians cannot 'fall away' and thus apostates who leave were really just feigning Christianity in the first place. Other Southern Baptists believe that people do genuinely believe, but then later reject God.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Apostates are socially shunned and/or publicly vilified:

– Yes

Notes: Southern Baptists generally have a policy of "excommunication" for members who abandon Christianity. Christians who are excommunicated are not seen to be on good terms with God and the Church. This means that the apostate would no longer

be viewed as an active member and would not be allowed to receive Communion or vote on church matters. It may even mean that the apostate is not allowed to attend church services. Active members may even be encouraged to not "fellowship" with apostates outside the church. The goal of excommunication is restorative rather than punitive. In other words, the rationale behind excommunication is to communicate that the apostate is no longer in good standing within the Christian community and stands in judgement before God. The hope is that an apostate would feel the weight of the loss of fellowship with God and the church and repent of the apostasy. Those who genuinely repent of apostasy/sins are welcomed back within the community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Wealth, civil rights, and/or social capital are taken by authorities:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Do apostates receive corporal punishment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Do apostates receive divine punishment:

– Yes

Notes: If a person becomes an apostate (i.e. deny Jesus), then it is believed that they will experience God's eternal judgement. There is some debate among Southern Baptists on whether apostates were genuinely Christians in the first place. Many hold that true Christians cannot 'fall away' and thus apostates who deny Christ/leave the Church were really just feigning Christianity in the first place. Other Southern Baptists believe that people do genuinely believe, but then later reject God. In either case, apostates are expected to receive a greater divine judgement for having known the truth and participating in it.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Punished in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Those who deny/reject Jesus are subject to eternal punishment in Hell. Southern Baptists typically depict Hell as a place of eternal conscious torment away from the relational presence of God. By rejecting Jesus' sacrifice for sin, apostates have lost the only way for being relationally reunited with God and thus are punished for their sins.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Cursed by "high god":

– Yes

Notes: If someone denies/rejects Jesus, then God punishes them in Hell for their rejection of God. Eternal life is fundamentally depicted as a sinless life in proper relationship to God. Therefore, Hell is the logical outcome/punishment of rejecting God. Southern Baptists typically depict Hell as a place of eternal conscious torment away from the relational presence of God. By rejecting Jesus' sacrifice for sin, apostates have lost the only way for being relationally reunited with God and thus are punished for their sins.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Cursed by other supernatural being(s):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Other divine punishment:

– Yes [specify]: Severer Punishment

Notes: Some Southern Baptists believe that apostates receive a greater divine judgement for having known the truth and participated in it. The terms of the severity of punishment is not indicated. Only that apostates would be judged more severely.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 14000000

Notes: This number is based on the combination of all Southern Baptist church members as recorded in the SBC's Annual Church Profile Statistical Summary 2020. While the SBC have 14 million official members, the weekly average for attendance was 4,439,797. (See https://research.lifeway.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/ACP_Summary_2020.pdf).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– I don't know

Notes: It is not clearly delineated how the 14000000 members are divided geographically.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large religious group (intolerant of other affiliations)

Notes: Southern Baptists are "exclusivists". This means that they believe that salvation is found in Jesus alone. In other words, Christianity is considered the only true religion. This does not, however, imply that Southern Baptists think they are the only true branch of Christianity. Southern Baptists believe adherents of other Christian denominations/traditions/branches can be authentic Christians outside of the SBC. The Baptist Faith and Message states, "the church [i]s the Body of Christ which includes all of the redeemed of all the ages, believers from every tribe, and tongue, and people, and nation" (BFM Article VI).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: Southern Baptists affirm the autonomy of local congregations. In other words, each individual church appoints in own leaders and set the parameters concerning authority and accountability. The Baptist Faith and Message states, "Each congregation operates under the Lordship of Christ through democratic processes. In such a congregation each member is responsible and accountable to Christ as Lord. Its scriptural officers are pastors and deacons. While both men and women are gifted for service in the church, the office of pastor is limited to men as qualified by Scripture" (BFM Article VI). While there is no central figure of authority, the SBC appoints a president annually with a maximum of two terms. The president's role includes "appoint[ing] the Credentials Committee (Bylaw 8B), tellers (Bylaw 10D), the Committee on Committees (Bylaw 19), and the Committee on Resolutions (Bylaw 20). He is also a member of the Committee on Order of Business (Bylaw 21) and an ex officio member of the boards of the Executive Committee, International Mission Board, North American Mission Board, LifeWay Christian Resources, and GuideStone Financial Resources (SBC Constitution, Article V). He presides over the SBC annual meeting with assistance from SBC parliamentarians (Bylaw 11). He may also call special meetings of the Convention with the concurrence of the other officers of the Convention and of the Executive Committee (SBC Constitution, Article XI). The president acts as the face of the Convention as a fraternal messenger to the annual sessions of the American Baptist Churches and the National Baptist

conventions (Bylaw 17). Unofficially, the president represents the Convention to the media and outside publics." (<https://www.baptistpress.com/resource-library/sbc-life-articles/sbc-presidents/>).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

Notes: It depends on the local church, but in general, there is usually a senior/lead pastor who is main leader of the local church. Some churches contain other pastors, elders, or deacons who may share equal or lesser authority with the senior pastor. In general, the pastor is held accountable to the community. This accountability is often mediated through other church leaders (pastors, elders, deacons, etc.)

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: Each congregation sets its own authorities in place. In other words, pastors of other SBC congregations do not have any authority outside their own local congregations. (Baptist Faith and Message Article VI). In some cases, the SBC executive committee can disfellowship local SBC churches for violating ethical and theological principles. Although, it is more likely that disfellowship would occur first from the disciplined church's state convention rather than the national level. (<https://www.tennessean.com/story/news/religion/2021/02/23/southern-baptists-expel-churches-sex-abuse-homosexuality/4497855001/>).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– No

Notes: Each congregation is run by its own local leaders. Each state, however, does have state and local/regional associations (often called conventions).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

Notes: There is no central figure of authority overseeing all SBC leaders. The SBC does, however, appoint a president annually with a maximum of two terms. The president's

role includes "appoint[ing] the Credentials Committee (Bylaw 8B), tellers (Bylaw 10D), the Committee on Committees (Bylaw 19), and the Committee on Resolutions (Bylaw 20). He is also a member of the Committee on Order of Business (Bylaw 21) and an ex officio member of the boards of the Executive Committee, International Mission Board, North American Mission Board, LifeWay Christian Resources, and GuideStone Financial Resources (SBC Constitution, Article V). He presides over the SBC annual meeting with assistance from SBC parliamentarians (Bylaw 11). He may also call special meetings of the Convention with the concurrence of the other officers of the Convention and of the Executive Committee (SBC Constitution, Article XI). The president acts as the face of the Convention as a fraternal messenger to the annual sessions of the American Baptist Churches and the National Baptist conventions (Bylaw 17). Unofficially, the president represents the Convention to the media and outside publics." (<https://www.baptistpress.com/resource-library/sbc-life-articles/sbc-presidents/>).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

Notes: The SBC describes itself as "a body of like-minded local churches cooperating together to reach the world with the Good News of Jesus Christ...Each Southern Baptist church is autonomous and unique; only when viewed together can one grasp the diversity that is the Southern Baptist Convention" (<https://www.sbc.net/about/>).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 2

Notes: Southern Baptists defines its authority by "democratic processes" (Baptists Faith and Message Article VI). In general, there are two main levels of authority within a local Southern Baptist Church. The first level is the pastor (or pastors) who is selected to lead the congregation. The second level is the congregation itself. There is a back and forth between these two levels. In some sense, the pastor leads the congregation and in another sense, the pastor is held accountable to the church community. This church polity is often called "congregationalism".

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: Southern Baptists believe that all Christians have the Holy Spirit (third person/member of the Trinity) indwelling them to guide them and gift them with abilities to edify the church (1 Cor 12:4-11, 1 Cor 14:3-5, 12, 17, 26; Eph. 4:12). Many Christians believe that pastors maintain a special spiritual gift of teaching or leadership. (See Romans 12:6-8, 1 Corinthians 12:4-11, and 1

Corinthians 12:28 for spiritual gift lists). In reference to the role of the Holy Spirit in a Christian's life, the Baptist Faith and Messages states, "He cultivates Christian character, comforts believers, and bestows the spiritual gifts by which they serve God through His church. He seals the believer unto the day of final redemption. His presence in the Christian is the guarantee that God will bring the believer into the fullness of the stature of Christ. He enlightens and empowers the believer and the church in worship, evangelism, and service" (BFM Article II. C).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– No

Notes: Southern Baptists believe humans only live one lifetime on earth before being resurrected and judged resulting in inheriting eternal life or eternal damnation (Baptist Faith and Message Article X).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:

– No

Notes: There may be some sense in which God directs Christians to cultivate their spiritual gifts through various level of experience. In general, God grants the spiritual gifts to individuals as he sees fit.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Powers are inherited:

– Yes

Notes: Southern Baptist believe that Christians inherit spiritual gifts from the Holy Spirit. Spiritual gifts may include: prophecy, serving, teaching, giving, exhortation, generosity, leadership, mercy, wisdom, knowledge, faith, healing, working of miracles, distinguishing between spirits, speaking in tongue, interpreting tongues, administration, etc. Most Southern Baptists are "cessationists" in that they believe certain spiritual gifts (such as speaking in tongues) has ceased in the eras beyond the first generation of Christians.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: The Holy Spirit (the third person/member of the Trinity) indwells Christians when they have faith in Jesus and imparts spiritual gifts. The Baptist Faith and Message states that the Holy Spirit "cultivates Christian character, comforts believers,

and bestows the spiritual gifts by which they serve God through His church" (BFM Article II. C).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):

– No

Notes: Southern Baptist sometimes partake in "laying on of hands", but this is usually understood as a symbolic form of commissioning rather than a transfer of spiritual power. For example, when a Southern Baptist gets ordained, other ordained pastors may lay their hands on him as a sign of affirmation and a sign of commissioning the newly ordained person to serve as a pastor.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:

– Yes

Notes: Southern Baptists believe that Pastors are often given the spiritual gifts of teaching, exhortation leading, and administration by the Holy Spirit.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

Notes: Southern Baptist churches are autonomously governed by the local communities through a democratic process. Generally, a committee appointed by the congregation will field applications and interviews. Applicants are generally required to perform some task (i.e. preach to the congregation) within the community to display their ability to fulfill the desired role. If the applicant seems to fit the role well, the committee will put him forward as a primary candidate. The congregation will then vote on affirming him. Depending on the church, it may require majority support or unanimous support.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– No

Notes: Pastors may recommend their replacement to the congregation, but the congregation has to approve it.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– No

Notes: Generally, a committee appointed by the congregation will field applications and interviews for future candidates. The congregation has to approve of the selected candidate.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– Yes

Notes: Generally, a committee appointed by the congregation will field applications and interviews for future candidates. The congregation has to approve of the selected candidate. Depending on the church, it may require majority support or unanimous support.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– Yes

Notes: Southern Baptists follow a polity of "congregationalism" in which the congregation selects its leaders. Generally, a committee appointed by the congregation will field applications and interviews. Applicants are generally required to perform some task (i.e. preach to the congregation) within the community to display their ability to fulfill the desired role. If the applicant seems to fit the role well, the committee will put him forward as a primary candidate. The congregation will then vote on affirming him. Depending on the church, it may require majority support or unanimous support.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

Notes: The selection of a local church's leaders are left up to the individual congregations.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– Yes

Notes: Generally, Southern Baptists pray that God lead them to the correct candidate.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– No

Notes: Southern Baptists believe that all humans are fallible and subject error due to humanity's sinful condition (Baptist Faith and Message Article III).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Notes: Due to the sinful condition of humanity, no Christian should unquestioningly obey their leaders. Southern Baptists do, however, believe that Christians should submit to their church leaders in general provided that it does not violate a command of Scripture.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: Southern Baptists affirm the Reformation principle of "sola scriptura" in which the Bible (Old and New Testaments) is the primary authoritative source for Christians. This is not to suggest that it is the only source of authority, but the primary/superior source. The Baptist Faith and Message describes the Southern Baptist view of the Bible in following manner: "The Holy Bible was written by men divinely inspired and is God's revelation of Himself to man. It is a perfect treasure of divine instruction. It has God for its author, salvation for its end, and truth, without any mixture of error, for its matter. Therefore, all Scripture is totally true and trustworthy. It reveals the principles by which God judges us, and therefore is, and will remain to the end of the world, the true center of Christian union, and the supreme standard by which all human conduct, creeds, and religious opinions should be tried. All Scripture is a testimony to Christ, who is Himself the focus of divine revelation" (BFM Article I).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Are they oral:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

Notes: The Baptist Faith and Message states, "The Holy Bible was written by men divinely inspired and is God's revelation of Himself to man. It is a perfect treasure of divine instruction. It has God for its author, salvation for its end, and truth, without any mixture of error, for its matter" (BFM Article I).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

Notes: The Baptist Faith and Message states, "The Holy Bible was written by men divinely inspired and is God's revelation of Himself to man. It is a perfect treasure of divine instruction. It has God for its author, salvation for its end, and truth, without any mixture of error, for its matter" (BFM Article I).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

Notes: The Bible is often described as the "Word of God". Southern Baptists affirm that God revealed the Bible/Scriptures (Old and New Testament) to various human authors while not overriding their particular personalities, writing styles, etc. In other words, Southern Baptists do not believe that God inspired the Bible in a strictly mechanical dictation fashion. Yet, the Bible is not merely a product of human creation or creativity. The Bible is revealed from God, but humans play a role in fashioning the texts. The Bible is neither wholly divine (no human element) nor wholly human (no divine element).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

Notes: It does not "originate" from humans in the formal sense. Yet, humans play an important role in the formation of the Bible. Southern Baptists affirm that God revealed the Bible/Scriptures (Old and New Testament) to various human authors while not overriding their particular personalities, writing styles, etc. In other words, Southern Baptists do not believe that God inspired the Bible in a strictly mechanical dictation fashion. Yet, the Bible is not merely a product of human creation or creativity. The Bible is revealed from God, but humans play a role in fashioning the texts. The Bible is neither wholly divine (no human element) nor wholly human (no divine element).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

Notes: Southern Baptists believe that the 66 books of the Bible (Old and New Testament) are the final canon (standard) and therefore should not be altered.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

Notes: Southern Baptists affirm that all Christians are able to interpret the Bible.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– No

Notes: Although, Southern Baptists emphasize the importance of knowing the original languages of Hebrew (for the Old Testament) and Greek (for the New Testament) for the process of translating the biblical text into other languages.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: Although, there is no specific historical moment/event for the official canonization of the Bible for Southern Baptists, they affirm the traditional 66 books of the Bible. 39 being found in the Old Testament and 27 being found in the New Testament. Southern Baptists reject the deuterocanonical/apocryphal books accepted by the Catholic Church.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: Some traditional Southern Baptists churches have steeples. Beyond this, Southern Baptists utilize a very basic and pragmatic approach to Church architecture. In general, Southern Baptists (and more widely Protestants) frown upon the perceived extravagance found in Catholic and Orthodox architecture. The extravagance is said to distract from the main focus of God. Thus, Southern Baptists opt for a plain/simple aesthetic with the pulpit (where the preacher gives his sermon) as the center of the sanctuary (the place of congregational gathering for church services). The centering of the pulpit is meant to communicate the importance of receiving God's word via the preacher's homily.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: Southern Baptists utilize a very basic and pragmatic approach to Church architecture. In

general, Southern Baptists (and more widely Protestants) frown upon the perceived extravagance found in Catholic and Orthodox architecture. The extravagance is said to distract from the main focus of God. Thus, Southern Baptists opt for a plain/simple aesthetic with the pulpit (where the preacher gives his sermon) as the center of the sanctuary (the place of congregational gathering for church services). The centering of the pulpit is meant to communicate the importance of receiving God's word via the preacher's homily.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Is iconography present:

– No

Notes: Southern Baptists reject the use of icons fearing that it comes close to idolatry. Therefore, Southern Baptists opt for a plain/simple aesthetic with the pulpit (where the preacher gives his sermon) as the center of the sanctuary (the place of congregational gathering for church services). The centering of the pulpit is meant to communicate the importance of receiving God's word via the preacher's homily.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– No

Notes: Southern Baptists churches typically have "sanctuaries", which is the main room in which the congregation gathers for church services. In general, however, it is not considered a sacred space although it may be treated with some reverence since their main services are conducted there.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: Southern Baptists do not have pilgrimages, but they often coordinate trips to the "Holy Land" (Israel) to visit the main sites of Jesus' ministry as well as other related biblical events.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that

some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: Southern Baptists affirm that humans have spirits that are able to continue living even after physical death. Although, the eternal state is when the deceased person's spirit is given a resurrected incorruptible body (Baptist Faith and Message Article X).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: Generally, the spirit is seen as the essence of the human.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: Southern Baptist believe that the spirit is distinct from the body and does survive after physical death.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The Baptist Faith and Message states, "The unrighteous will be consigned to Hell, the place of everlasting punishment. The righteous in their resurrected and glorified bodies will receive their reward and will dwell forever in Heaven with the Lord." (BFM Article X).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: There is a distinction between the temporal and final states. In the temporal state, disembodied Christian spirits go to be with God in Heaven (God's dwelling place) until Jesus'

second coming in which he purifies and judges the world. In the final state, the disembodied Christian spirit is given a resurrected body in New Jerusalem (a phrase indicating a renewed earth) to dwell with God eternally (Revelation 21-22). Alternatively, non-Christian disembodied spirits wait for judgment in Hades (the temporal state) until they are given a resurrected body, which is judged eternally in Hell (the final state).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Notes: One must distinguish between the temporal and final states to answer this question accurately. In the temporal state, disembodied Christian spirits go to be with God in Heaven (God's dwelling place) until Jesus' second coming in which he purifies and judges the world. The final state, however, is when resurrected bodies dwell on the renewed earth (New Jerusalem) with God. In other words, Heaven (God's dwelling place) merges with earth (humanity's dwelling place). In this sense, the final (eternal) state is on earth.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– No

Notes: Although, it sometimes symbolically referred to as "above".

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Afterlife located in "other" space:

– Yes [specify]: Renewed Earth

Notes: The renewed (or purified) earth is the final state of dwelling for resurrected Christians. It is referred to as New Jerusalem. Jerusalem refers to the major place of

worship in the Old Testament (location of main Jewish Temple).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: Southern Baptists do not believe in reincarnation, but do believe all humans will be resurrected at the end of the ages to receive divine reward or judgement.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Are grave goods present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

As cenotaphs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: Generally, cemeteries are used because this is a common American practice. Some Southern Baptists, however, believe that physical burial represents hope in the future resurrection of the body. Others think cremation is permissible because the resurrected body will be distinct from the earthly body. All Southern Baptists agree that God will raise everyone with a resurrected body regardless of what remains of their physical bodies (i.e. burial, cremation, decayed, destroyed, etc.).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: The Baptist Faith and Message describes God in the following way: "There is one and only one living and true God. He is an intelligent, spiritual, and personal Being, the Creator, Redeemer, Preserver, and Ruler of the universe. God is infinite in holiness and all other perfections. God is all powerful and all knowing; and His perfect knowledge extends to all things, past, present, and future, including the future decisions of His free creatures. To Him we owe the highest love, reverence, and obedience. The eternal triune God reveals Himself to us as Father, Son, and Holy Spirit, with distinct personal attributes, but without division of nature, essence, or being" (BFM Article II).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: The Baptist Faith and Message describes God in the following way: "There is one and only one living and true God. He is an intelligent, spiritual, and personal Being, the Creator, Redeemer, Preserver, and Ruler of the universe. God is infinite in holiness and all other perfections. God is all powerful and all knowing; and His perfect knowledge extends to all things, past, present, and future, including the future decisions of His free creatures. To Him we owe the highest love, reverence, and obedience. The eternal triune God reveals Himself to us as Father, Son, and Holy Spirit, with distinct personal attributes, but without division of nature, essence, or being" (BFM Article II).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

Notes: God is considered to be a spiritual/metaphysical being who does not have a physical body. Biblical writers, however, often use anthropomorphic terms to describe God. In other words, anthropomorphic terms help humans to understand God.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: Although, Jesus (the second person of the Trinity) is considered to be the Messiah, which is a Hebrew term for a Davidic king. Since Jesus is God and Man, there is some sense in which God is fused with the concept of monarchy.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Notes: Although, Jesus (the second person of the Trinity) is considered to be the Messiah, which is a Hebrew term for a Davidic king. Since Jesus is God and Man, there is some sense in which God is fused with the concept of monarchy.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: The Baptist Faith and Message states, "God is infinite in holiness and all other perfections" (BFM Article II).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: The Baptist Faith and Message states that God is "all knowing and His perfect knowledge extends to all things, past, present, and future, including the future decisions of His free creatures" (BFM Article II).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of

human affairs:

— No

Notes: God is considered to be omniscient.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

— Yes

Notes: God is considered to be omniscient.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

— Yes

Notes: God is considered to be omniscient.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: It is a common motif in the Old and New Testament that God knows the human heart.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: The Baptist Faith and Message states that God's "perfect knowledge extends to all things, past, present, and future, including the future decisions of His free creatures" (BFM Article II).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: God is omniscient

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Southern Baptists believe that God is providentially active in the world and in human affairs bringing about his purposes/ends.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Biblical writers often use anthropomorphic terms to display God as having emotions similar to humans. Theologically, however, Christians hold that God is impassible.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Biblical writers often use anthropomorphic terms to display God as having emotions similar to humans. Theologically, however, Christians hold that God is impassible.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

Notes: Southern Baptists believe that God alone is to be worshipped. Many cite the ten commandments (found in Exodus 20:1-17) as a clear prohibition of worshipping other beings.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Notes: Southern Baptists believe that God communicated directly with prophets in the Old Testament and through Jesus in the New Testament. Additionally, the Bible is considered to be a divinely revealed/inspired work (Baptist Faith and Message Article I).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: This is the primary method found in the Bible.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ In trance possession:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

Notes: Divination is strictly prohibited in Old Testament (Leviticus 19:31 and Deuteronomy 18:9-12).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: Southern Baptists believe that a deceased person's disembodied spirit goes to be with God (awaiting resurrection/New Jerusalem) in Heaven or awaits resurrection and final judgement (Hell).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is unclear what knowledge disembodied spirits have.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is unclear what memories disembodied spirits have access to.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Disembodied spirits in the presence of God display positive emotions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is presumed that disembodied spirits awaiting judgement display negative emotions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– No

Notes: Although, there is one instance in 1 Samuel 28:3-25 (Old Testament) where Samuel the prophet's spirit is called upon by King Saul through a Medium. Samuel's spirit condemns Saul's action.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Southern Baptists affirm the presence of angels (messengers of God) and demons (fallen angelic beings who seek to sow chaos in God's creation).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: God does allow Angels to physically manifest in the Biblical texts, but they are not inherently visible. Demons can possess people, but they do not physically manifest on their own.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: Angels do not usually physically interact with humans. Demons can physically possess humans.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: It is unclear the extent to which angels/demons have of knowledge this world. God alone, however, is said to be omniscient.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Notes: It is unclear the extent to which angels/demons have of knowledge this world, but only God is said to be omniscient.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is unclear what angles and demons can see.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is unclear what angles and demons can see.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– I don't know

Notes: It is unclear what angles and demons can see.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal

essence):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is unclear what angels and demons know about humans.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

Notes: Only God knows the future.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– No

Notes: Angels can reward if God sends them to do so.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

Notes: Angels can punish if God sends them to do so. Demons are able to possess humans and cause them to suffer.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– No

Notes: Angels are depicted as worshipping God.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– No

Notes: Demons do react negatively to encounters with Jesus.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Southern Baptists believe that Jesus is fully God and fully man. He is considered to be the only divine-human being (Baptist Faith and Message Article II. B).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: During Jesus' earthly ministry and after his resurrection, he was physically seen.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: During Jesus' earthly ministry and after his resurrection, he was able to be physically felt.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: While Jesus restricted his knowledge during His earthly ministry, it is believed that he is omniscient.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus is believed to be omniscient.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus is believed to be omniscient.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

— Yes

Notes: Jesus is believed to be omniscient.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

— Yes

Notes: Jesus is believed to be omniscient.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

— Yes

Notes: Jesus is believed to be omniscient.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Mixed human-divine beings know your basic character (personal essence):

— Yes

Notes: Jesus is believed to be omniscient.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Mixed human-divine beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

— Yes

Notes: Jesus is believed to be omniscient.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have other knowledge of the human world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus is believed to be providentially active in world affairs.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can reward:

– Yes

Notes: It is believed that Jesus rewards Christians.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can punish:

– Yes

Notes: It is believed that Jesus will punish non-believers.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus was described as exhibiting positive emotions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus was described as exhibiting positive emotions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus was described as experiencing hunger.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus was described as communicating with humans during his earthly ministry, but is also said to reach out to humans after his resurrection/ascension (see Paul's conversion in Acts 9).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ In trance possession:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Southern Baptists acknowledge the presence of God, angels, Satan, and demons.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Notes: The term "archangel" implies some level of hierarchy among angels. Satan is also understood as "chief" of the demons.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Notes: Although it is unclear exactly what parameters are in place.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: Since God is omniscient, he sees all things. God will ultimately judge humans for their actions and whether they had faith in him. The Baptist Faith and Message states, "Jesus Christ will return personally and visibly in glory to the earth; the dead will be raised; and Christ will judge all men in righteousness. The unrighteous will be consigned to Hell, the place of everlasting punishment. The righteous in their resurrected and glorified bodies will receive their reward and will dwell forever in Heaven with the Lord" (BFM Article X).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Christians are expected to keep moral norms specific to being in covenant with God (i.e. commands found in the Bible). Some moral norms are universal in which Christians and non-Christians are expected to obey and will be held accountable on judgement day.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: Murder is considered to be morally impermissible for all humans (Christian or non-Christian).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: Murder is considered to be morally impermissible for all humans (Christian or non-Christian).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Notes: Murder is considered to be morally impermissible for all humans (Christian or non-Christian).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Notes: Southern Baptists believe that monogamous heterosexual marriage is the only moral expression of sexuality. The Baptist Faith and Message states, "Marriage is the uniting of one man and one woman in covenant commitment for a lifetime...[and] the channel of sexual expression according to biblical standards..." (BFM Article XVIII).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Notes: Adultery is consider morally impermissible for all humans.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ **Incest:**

– Yes

Notes: Incest is consider morally impermissible for all humans.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ **Other sexual practices:**

– Yes [specify]: Homosexuality

Notes: Homosexuality is consider morally impermissible for all humans.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ **Supernatural beings care about lying:**

– Yes

Notes: Lying is consider morally impermissible for all humans.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ **Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:**

– Yes

Notes: Humans are expected to keep their word.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ **Supernatural beings care about laziness:**

– Yes

Notes: Christians are expected to work in order to be able to sustain their life.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ **Supernatural beings care about sorcery:**

– Yes

Notes: Sorcery is morally prohibited.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Southern Baptists do not have a clear perspective on whether God cares about such things as boxing, etc.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Southern Baptists do not have a clear perspective on whether God cares about shirking risk.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Notes: Christians are expected to respect their elders.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

Notes: Gossiping is viewed as morally impermissible.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Notes: Property crimes would be considered morally impermissible.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Notes: Christians are commanded to share the Gospel and make disciples.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Notes: In the Bible, God often condemns the rich for their lack of concern and oppression of the needy. Christians are expected to share among themselves and meet each other's needs.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There are not clear commands regarding personal hygiene in the New Testament. Some commands pertain to personal hygiene in the Old Testament, but these commands were only obligatory for the Israelites in the old covenant. Generally, Southern Baptists encourage proper hygiene as a matter of stewardship before God (Baptist Faith and Message Article XIII).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: God is the one who metes out punishment. Punishment could be temporal or eternal. Temporal

punishment may be in response to some sin. Eternal punishment is the final judgement for those who rejected Jesus and for the sins they committed on earth.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Notes: Although, God may use his angels as the medium of punishment.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

Notes: Although some consequences for sin may occur naturally.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: Temporal punishments may be a response to sins. Eternal punishment is for the rejection of Jesus and sins committed on earth.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The Baptist Faith and Message states, "Jesus Christ will return personally and visibly in glory to the earth; the dead will be raised; and Christ will judge all men in righteousness. The unrighteous will be consigned to Hell, the place of everlasting punishment. The righteous in their resurrected and glorified bodies will receive their reward and will dwell forever in Heaven with the Lord" (BFM Article X).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: Hell is described in terms of extreme anguish (i.e. weeping, gnashing of teeth, unquenchable fire, etc.)

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: Some temporal punishments from God may be present in life, but it is often difficult to determine if the suffering/punishment is due to a particular sin.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– No

Notes: In the Old Testament, political failure could be the result of God's judgement for sin among the Israelites.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– No

Notes: In the Old Testament, defeat in battle could be the result of God's judgement for sin among the Israelites..

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– No

Notes: In the Old Testament, crop failure or bad weather could be the result of God's judgement for sin .

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– No

Notes: Although, there are some instances in the Old Testament where illness is a punishment for sin. In the Old/New Testament, sickness/illness does not necessarily indicate that one has sinned.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– No

Notes: In the Old Testament, among the Israelites, descendants may inherit difficulties/curses as a result of their ancestors' faithlessness.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Notes: God is the one who gives rewards. Rewards could be temporal or eternal. Temporal rewards may be in response to living according to God's standards. Eternal life with God is primary reward for Christians, but specific Christian rewards will vary based on how a person lived faithfully before God.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

Notes: Although some benefits for right living may occur naturally.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The Baptist Faith and Message states, "The righteous in their resurrected and glorified bodies will receive their reward and will dwell forever in Heaven with the Lord" (BFM Article X).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

Notes: Eternal life with God is the main reward. Relational life with God is seen as humanity's main purpose in life.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: A life without sin and a life lived fully in God's presence results in true joy.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

Notes: A life without sin and a life lived fully in God's presence results in true joy.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

Notes: While Southern Baptists do not affirm reincarnation, eternal life is superior because it is without sin and the resurrected body is incorruptible. Christians also get to be fully in God's presence, which is seen as the ultimate reward.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– No

Notes: While Southern Baptists do not affirm reincarnation, eternal life in the renewed world is superior because it is a world without sin and is incorruptible. The renewed world is also superior because God's presence is fully there.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– No

Notes: In the Old Testament, among the Israelites, political success could be God's reward for obeying his commandments.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– No

Notes: In the Old Testament, among the Israelites, success in battle could be God's reward for obeying his commandments.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– No

Notes: In the Old Testament, among the Israelites, peace and social stability could be God's reward for obeying his commandments.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

Notes: In the Old Testament, among the Israelites, healthy crops and good weather could be God's reward for obeying his commandments.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– No

Notes: In the Old Testament, among the Israelites, health could be God's reward for obeying his commandments.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– No

Notes: In the Old Testament, among the Israelites, children could be seen as a blessing from God.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– No

Notes: In the Old Testament, among the Israelites, descendants may inherit blessings as a result of their ancestors' faithfulness.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus is understood to be the Messiah as prophesied in the Old Testament.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Alive, identified:

– Yes

Notes: Southern Baptists believe that Jesus is the Messiah and is alive eternally after conquering death.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Coming in this lifetime:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The date of the second coming of Jesus is not known although there is motif of imminence present in the New Testament.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Coming on specified date:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The date of the second coming of Jesus is not known although there is motif of imminence present in the New Testament.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The date of the second coming of Jesus is not known although there is motif of imminence present in the New Testament.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Coming has already passed:

– No

Notes: Southern Baptist believe in two comings of the Messiah. The first coming was Jesus' life, ministry, death, and resurrection. These events have already occurred. The second coming is when Jesus returns again to bring an end to sin, judge all humans, and usher in the renewed world. This coming has not yet occurred.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs:

– No

Notes: Although the term messiah was applied to various Davidic kings, Jesus is considered to be the penultimate and long-hoped for Messiah.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

Notes: Southern Baptists believe there are two major purposes connected with the two comings of the Messiah. The first coming was Jesus' life, ministry, death, and resurrection. Jesus is said to have taken all of humanity's sin upon himself in his death on the cross acting as a substitute for condemned humanity. His resurrection is God's vindication of him and a sign of conquering the penalty of sin. Jesus is the mediator between God and humanity. In Jesus' second coming, he will bring an end to sin, judge all humans, and usher in the renewed world. The Baptist Faith and Message states, "Salvation involves the redemption of the whole man, and is offered freely to all who accept Jesus Christ as Lord and Saviour, who by His own blood obtained eternal redemption for the believer. In its broadest sense salvation includes regeneration, justification, sanctification, and glorification. There is no salvation apart from personal faith in Jesus Christ as Lord" (BFM Article IV).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus is described as a king who will rule the renewed world.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus is considered to be the true "high priest" who mediates between God and humanity.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: Salvation

Notes: Southern Baptists believe that by putting faith in Jesus the Messiah, a person's sins are forgiven and they are saved from the consequences of sin. Because of Jesus' work of redemption, humans are able to be relationally restored to God. The Baptist Faith and Message states, "Salvation involves the redemption of the whole man, and is offered freely to all who accept Jesus Christ as Lord and Saviour, who by His own blood obtained eternal redemption for the believer. In its broadest sense salvation includes regeneration, justification, sanctification, and glorification. There is no salvation apart from personal faith in Jesus Christ as Lord" (BFM Article IV).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

Notes: The Baptist Faith and Message states, "God, in His own time and in His own way, will bring the world to its appropriate end. According to His promise, Jesus Christ will return personally and visibly in glory to the earth; the dead will be raised; and Christ will judge all men in righteousness. The unrighteous will be consigned to Hell, the place of everlasting punishment. The righteous in their resurrected and glorified bodies will receive their reward and will dwell forever in Heaven with the Lord" (BFM Article X).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Baptist Faith and Message states, "God, in His own time and in His own way, will bring the world to its appropriate end" (BFM Article X).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Baptist Faith and Message states, "God, in His own time and in His own way, will bring the world to its appropriate end" (BFM Article X).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Baptist Faith and Message states, "God, in His own time and in His own way, will bring the world to its appropriate end" (BFM Article X).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Baptist Faith and Message states, "God, in His own time and in His own way, will bring the world to its appropriate end" (BFM Article X).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– No

Notes: The Baptist Faith and Message states, "God, in His own time and in His own way, will bring the world to its appropriate end" (BFM Article X).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

Notes: The Baptist Faith and Message states, "According to His promise, Jesus Christ will return personally and visibly in glory to the earth; the dead will be raised; and Christ will judge all men in righteousness. The unrighteous will be consigned to Hell, the place of everlasting punishment. The righteous in their resurrected and glorified bodies will receive their reward

and will dwell forever in Heaven with the Lord" (BFM Article X).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Yes

Notes: Southern Baptists believe that the final state of humanity is on a renewed earth (referred to in Revelation 21-22 as New Jerusalem) in which there is no more sin or suffering and Christians can behold God "face to face".

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– Yes

Notes: The beginning of the final state (eternity).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– Yes

Notes: The Triune God will reign as king.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– Yes

Notes: It is new in the sense that Christians can actually behold God. God fully dwells in the midst of humanity. There is no temple because God Himself is the temple (Revelation 21-22).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– Yes

Notes: It is believed that every human will experience death, be resurrected, and judged by God before entering the final state (New Jerusalem or Hell). Christians will experience life with God for eternity while non-Christians will suffer for their sins in Hell.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

Notes: All resurrected Christians will live for eternity with God on the renewed earth.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

Notes: In a sense, everyone survives the eschaton because every person will be resurrected and judged and live eternally either in the renewed earth with God or punished in Hell.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Other survival condition:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The Baptist Faith and Message States, "All Christians are under obligation to seek to make the will of Christ supreme in our own lives and in human society. Means and methods used for the improvement of society and the establishment of righteousness among men can be truly and permanently helpful only when they are rooted in the regeneration of the individual by the saving grace of God in Jesus Christ. In the spirit of Christ, Christians should oppose racism, every form of greed, selfishness, and vice, and all forms of sexual immorality, including adultery, homosexuality, and

pornography. We should work to provide for the orphaned, the needy, the abused, the aged, the helpless, and the sick. We should speak on behalf of the unborn and contend for the sanctity of all human life from conception to natural death. Every Christian should seek to bring industry, government, and society as a whole under the sway of the principles of righteousness, truth, and brotherly love. In order to promote these ends Christians should be ready to work with all men of good will in any good cause, always being careful to act in the spirit of love without compromising their loyalty to Christ and His truth." (BFM Article XV).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

What is the nature of this distinction:

– Strongly present and highlighted

Notes: Southern Baptists believe that Christians should be subject to civil authorities and laws as long as they accord with Christian moral norms. Christians moral norms are understood to be commands given by God in the Bible. The Baptist Faith and Message states that the Bible "reveals the principles by which God judges us, and therefore is, and will remain to the end of the world, the true center of Christian union, and the supreme standard by which all human conduct, creeds, and religious opinions should be tried" (BFM Article I).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Christians moral norms are understood to be commands given by God in the Bible. The Baptist Faith and Message states that the Bible "reveals the principles by which God judges us, and therefore is, and will remain to the end of the world, the true center of Christian union, and the supreme standard by which all human conduct, creeds, and religious opinions should be tried" (BFM Article I).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

Notes: Southern Baptists believe that God is not metaphysically vague and has clearly communicated moral norms to humans.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

Notes: Moral norms are connected to God who is the giver of specified moral norms. There is some debate on whether there are objective moral norms outside of God or whether God determines right/wrong.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals (any time period)

Notes: There are different types/levels of moral norms. For example, some moral norms were specific to the Israelites in the old covenant (i.e. do not get a tattoo). Some moral norms are specific to Christians in the new covenant (i.e. make other Christian disciples). Some moral norms are universal (i.e. do not murder).

Specific to this answer:

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: Southern Baptists argue that sexuality is only properly expressed in a monogamous heterosexual marriage. The Baptist Faith and Message states, "Marriage is the uniting of one man and one woman in covenant commitment for a lifetime. It is God's unique gift to reveal the union between Christ and His church and to provide for the man and the woman in marriage the framework for intimate companionship, the channel of sexual expression according to biblical standards, and the means for procreation of the human race." (BFM Article XVIII). Southern Baptists also oppose "all forms of sexual immorality, including adultery, homosexuality, and pornography" (Baptist Faith and Message Article XV).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Monogamy (males):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Monogamy (females):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: Heterosexual relationships

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: Heterosexual relationships

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: While fasting is not mandatory, it is strongly encouraged as a spiritual practice.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Notes: Jesus declared "all foods clean" (Mark 7:19) distinguished from the mandatory kosher laws found in the old covenant.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: Southern Baptists believe Jesus was the "final sacrifice for sins". Human sacrifice is a morally impermissible religious practice.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: Southern Baptists believe Jesus was the "final sacrifice for sins". Human sacrifice is a morally impermissible religious practice.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: Southern Baptists believe suicide is morally impermissible because God is the giver of life and should determine when each person's life ends.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: Although Southern Baptists believe that 10% of one's income should be tithed (weekly/monthly) to one's local church in order to support the ministers and ministries of the church. The Baptist Faith and Message states, "God is the source of all blessings, temporal and spiritual; all that we have and are we owe to Him. Christians have a spiritual debtorship to the whole world, a holy trusteeship in the gospel, and a binding stewardship in their possessions. They are therefore under obligation to serve Him with their time, talents, and material possessions; and should recognize all these as entrusted to them to use for the glory of God and for helping others. According to the Scriptures, Christians should contribute of their means cheerfully, regularly, systematically, proportionately, and liberally for the advancement of the Redeemer's cause on earth" (BFM Article XIII).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

— Yes

Notes: Southern Baptists expect members to attend the weekly church service on Sunday. It may also be expected that they actively attend other smaller meetings (i.e. Sunday school/small group/education classes/church meetings, etc.) that occur outside of the main service. The Baptist Faith and Message states, "God is the source of all blessings, temporal and spiritual; all that we have and are we owe to Him. Christians have a spiritual debtorship to the whole world, a holy trusteeship in the gospel, and a binding stewardship in their possessions. They are therefore under obligation to serve Him with their time, talents, and material possessions; and should recognize all these as entrusted to them to use for the glory of God and for helping others. According to the Scriptures, Christians should contribute of their means cheerfully, regularly, systematically, proportionately, and liberally for the advancement of the Redeemer's cause on earth" (BFM Article XIII).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

— No

Notes: Although it is expected that Christians be willing to sacrifice their lives for the sake of their faith if necessary. Becoming a missionary may require physical risk taking.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

— Yes

Notes: Southern Baptists believe that Christians must adhere to all applicable commands given in the Bible. The Baptist Faith and Message describes the Bible as "the supreme standard by which all human conduct" (BFM Article I). The Baptist Faith and Message also states, "In the spirit of Christ, Christians should oppose racism, every form of greed, selfishness, and vice, and all forms of sexual immorality, including adultery, homosexuality, and pornography. We should work to provide for the orphaned, the needy, the abused, the aged, the helpless, and the sick. We should speak on behalf of the unborn and contend for the sanctity of all human life from conception to natural death. Every Christian should seek to bring industry, government, and society as a whole under the sway of the principles of righteousness, truth, and brotherly love. In order to promote these ends Christians should be ready to work with all men of good will in any good cause, always being careful to act in the spirit of love without compromising their loyalty to Christ and His truth" (BFM Article XV).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

— No

Notes: While it does not require marginalization of out-group members, it is expected that members be specially committed to caring for those within the church. Yet, there is also an expectation to care for those outside the church to meet spiritual and material needs (Baptist Faith and Message Article

XV).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Notes: Southern Baptists believe that most major Christian practices are conducted as a congregation. Although, there is an expectation that Christians would pray and read their Bibles as individuals and within their family unit (Baptist Faith and Message Article XVIII).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Notes: Southern Baptists believe that Christians should gather every Sunday to participate in congregational worship. Congregational worship will generally include singing, praying, and a sermon. Meetings may also include important Christian rituals such as Baptism and the Lord's Supper (Communion).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– I don't know

Notes: The specific answer depends on the local congregation in question. The numbers would also vary weekly.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 1

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of

governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: A local church's leaders (Pastors and deacons) oversee the orthodoxy of the church events.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Notes: A local church's leaders (Pastors and deacons) oversee the orthopraxy of the church events and rituals.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

Notes: Christians will sing songs, pray, and listen to the sermon together. The Lord's Supper is often consumed simultaneously (although the practice of when the elements are consumed varies among Southern Baptists churches).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Notes: In general, Southern Baptists frown on the use of alcohol and other intoxicants.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Notes: Southern Baptists sometimes refer to each other as a "brother" or "sister" in Christ. The New Testament makes frequent use of familial language in reference to Christians/the Church.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– No

Notes: Not all Southern Baptists employ familial language, but it is very common.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

Notes: Not all Southern Baptists employ familial language, but it is very common.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Southern Baptists describe themselves as "a body of like-minded local churches cooperating together to reach the world with the Good News of Jesus Christ" (Sbc.net, About the SBC).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: The SBC and local Southern Baptists churches seek to provide famine relief in local and international settings.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: American Southern Baptists can apply for aid from local and statewide authorities and charities.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: The Baptist Faith and Message states, "[Southern Baptists] should work to provide for the orphaned, the needy, the abused, the aged, the helpless, and the sick" (BFM Article XV).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: American Southern Baptists can apply for aid from local/statewide authorities and charities.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Notes: Southern Baptists do not have institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm, but support these endeavors. The Baptist Faith and Message states, "[Southern Baptists] should work to provide for the orphaned, the needy, the abused, the aged, the helpless, and the sick" (BFM Article XV).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: American Southern Baptists have access to local medical care.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: Southern Baptists offer formal educations through its six seminaries. Some of these seminaries also offer undergraduate education in addition to their standard graduate programs. The Baptist Faith and Message states, "In Christian education there should be a proper balance between academic freedom and academic responsibility. Freedom in any orderly relationship of human life is always limited and never absolute. The freedom of a teacher in a Christian school, college, or seminary is limited by the pre-eminence of Jesus Christ, by the authoritative nature of the Scriptures, and by the distinct purpose for which the school exists" (BFM Article XII). Southern Baptists churches also often offer informal training in local congregations.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Notes: While Seminary is generally attended by those seeking to be pastors or missionaries, anyone with a bachelor degree and a church leader's recommendation is able to attend. Some of the seminaries also have undergraduate programs as well.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: Although, females are not able to be ordained as pastors in Southern Baptist churches. A female can earn a Master of Divinity degree (the typical degree attained by Southern Baptist pastors), but are unable to serve as pastors.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Southern Baptists are permitted to seek education outside of Christian or Southern Baptists circles.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: In general, most members do not interact with the larger Southern Baptist Convention, but "messengers" are sent from local churches to elect a Southern Baptist president at the annual meetings. All Southern Baptists are welcomed to attend the annual meeting.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Southern Baptists are able to interact with any of the Southern Baptist entities and seminaries, but this is not typical. Southern Baptist entities include: SBC Executive Committee, International Mission Board, North American Mission Board, Lifeway Christian Resources, GuideStone Financial Resources, Ethics & Religious Liberty Commission, six Seminaries, and the Woman's Missionary Union.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: American Southern Baptists utilize the use of public food storage stores.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: American Southern Baptists utilize the use of local water management services.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: American Southern Baptists utilize the use of local transportation services.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: While it is not strictly required or levied, Southern Baptists believe that 10% of one's income should be tithed (weekly/monthly) to one's local church in order to support the ministers and ministries of the church. Individual Southern Baptist churches also give a percentage (determined by the local congregation) to the Southern Baptist Convention's cooperative program. The cooperative program is described as "[t]he financial fuel for reaching every person for Jesus Christ in every town, every city, every state, and every nation" (Sbc.net).

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: American Southern Baptists pay taxes to their federal government. Some states also have a local income tax.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: American Southern Baptists interact with local and federal authorities.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: American Southern Baptists interact with local and federal judicial systems.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: American Southern Baptists are subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by local and federal authorities.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: Capital punishment is permitted in 27 states.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: American Southern Baptists are subject to local and federal legal codes.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: American Southern Baptists are able to participate in the different branches of the American military.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: As American citizens, Southern Baptists are protected by the American military.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: There is no official language for the United States of America. English, however, is the most commonly used language.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: There is no official language for the United States of America. English, however, is the most commonly used language.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Southern Baptists follow the 12 month Gregorian Calendar used in America.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: There are various forms of food production in the United States of America. American Southern Baptists typically purchase food from supermarkets.

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Fishing
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Specific to this answer:

Region: U.S.A

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Report on Slavery and Racism in the History of the Southern Baptist Theological Seminary

Reference: Andy Beachum undefined, Rebecca Wolford. SBC Presidents. (undefined, Ed.) Baptist Press.

Reference: Annual Church Profile Statistical Summary

Reference: Southern Baptist Convention (Website)

Reference: Baptist Faith and Message